

A Taxonomy of Intelligent Algorithms used for Solving Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP) in the Year 2019.

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Abstract

Travel salesman problem (TSP) considered as one of the most important complex optimization problem. The complexity of TSP is due to many reasons, like different types of TSP, the number of visited cities, and the absence of real optimal solution to it. Many intelligent algorithms were proposed and enhanced to solve TSP, but none of them gave the real optimal solution; some solutions were close to the optimal solutions but with special conditions. In our research we reviewed related published articles in the year 2019(Scopus database), to find the state-of-art in Solving Travel Salesman Problem (TSP) by different intelligent algorithms. We reviewed 200 published articles in Scopus database, and found 128 related papers. The reviewed articles showed that; there are 34 types of TSP, 89 proposed and enhanced algorithms. The main type in reviewed articles was the symmetric TSP, where 82 articles from 128 reviewed articles discussed it. This research considered as road map for more research in this filed.

Keywords: travel salesman problem, symmetric TSP, algorithm, optimization.

Introduction

Travel salesman problem (TSP) is a complex computational issue in operational research science and considered as NP-hard problem type (non-deterministic polynomial-time hardness) [129]. TSP has in general two main types: symmetric TSP and asymmetric TSP, but there are many sub types like dynamic TSP (DTSP), Multi-commodity Traveling Salesman Problem with Priority Prizes (MTSPPP), angular-metric travelling salesman problem (AngleTSP).... etc....see table 1.

Solving TSP in general seems to be easy, but it is getting hard when the number of visited cities is increasing [130]. The literature showed that there a huge number of proposed solutions to solve TSP. Different heuristic and meta-heuristic intelligent algorithms were proposed and improved to solve different types of TSP. In this research we are going to show the proposed and improved solutions to TSP that published in the year 2019.

Methodology:

We are going to show all related published papers in Scopus database in the year 2019, determining the names of proposed algorithms, improved algorithms, and the different variants of TSP (see figure 1).

Figure 1: Methodology

Literature Review

Akhand, M.a.h., et al.[1] ,showed a new variant of spider monkey optimization (SMO) called dynamic spider monkey optimization (DSMO) for large symmetric TSP instances. Freitas&Penna[2] , proposed a hybrid heuristic algorithm , to solve a variant of symmetric TSP called , flying sidekick TSP.Bock &Klamroth[3], proposed a hybrid algorithm , called(MOTSRP) ,combined of the Multi-Objective TSP (MOTSP)and Multi-Objective Traveling Repairman Problem (MOTRP), to solve random instances for both problems .Shahmanzari, Masoud, et al.[4] proposed a two-phase matheuristic algorithm to solve Roaming Salesman Problem (RSP). Wang[5] , proposed a heuristic algorithm, with a binomial distribution model based on frequency to solve symmetric TSP. Munapo[6] proposed a network reconstruction technique with minimal spanning tree (MST) for symmetric TSP. Öztürk&Uslu[7] proposed a cantor-set based (CB) method for heuristic algorithms to solve symmetric TSP.Ohira, Ryoma, et al.[8] proposed a genetic algorithm called adaptive and modular genetic algorithm (AMGA) to solve symmetric TSP. Hameed[9], proposed a multi-objective genetic algorithm (MOGA) to find optimal solution for typical symmetric TSP.Ye, Hao, et al[10] proposed a self-exploration strategy added to chicken swarm algorithm to solve symmetric TSP.Halaoui[11] built a virtual graph by using different techniques like algorithm A* and graph Hamilton circuit algorithm to solve symmetric TSP.Silva, Tiago Tiburcio Da, et al.[12]proposed Biased Random-Key Genetic Algorithm (BRKGA) to solve medium and large Multicommodity Traveling Salesman Problem with Priority Prizes (MTSPPP).Moraes&Freitas[13] found that genetic algorithm performance was better than ant colony optimization and simulated annealing performance for Moving Target TSP (MT-TSP).Mohan, Usha, et al[14] discussed path version of the TSP and named it Biased-TSP-Path.Papalitsas, Christos, et al[15] discussed TSP with Time Windows, they anticipated that this method will lead to optimal solution for of small scale TSPTW instances.Ganesan[16] discussed " variance estimates for TSP Cn and prove that if the cities are well-connected in a certain sense, then TSP Cn appropriately centered and scaled converges to zero in probability" for Euclidean TSP.Khan, Indadul, et al. [17] proposed hybrid algorithm , combined of modified particle swarm optimization (PSO) and genetic algorithm (GA) ,used for symmetric and a symmetric TSP instances.Sengupta, Lahari, et al.[18] ,suggested a two new operators ("link swap and 3-permute") for open-loop variant TSP.Cygan, Marek, et al. [19] improved the k-OPT heuristic algorithm for symmetric TSP instances.Kaspi, Moshe, et al. [20] improved classical TSP algorithm by adding an iterative solution method for symmetric TSP instances.Myszkowski, Paweł B., et al. [21] proposed "Non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm II (NSGA-II) "for multi-objective TSP (MOTSP) .Júnior, &, Guimarães, [22] showed a " Greedy Randomized Adaptive Search Procedure (GRASP) metaheuristics" to solve symmetric TSP.Wang & Wu [23], proposed a heuristic model called frequency graph for symmetric TSP.

Sahai, Tuhin, et al. [24] constructed heuristic strategies based on adding the relaxed discrete optimization into suitable manifolds, for symmetric TSP. Arash, et al [25] improved Christofides algorithm for half-integer TSP. Bonnet, et al. [26] discussed Exponential Time Hypothesis in Hamiltonian cycle for symmetric TSP. Bossek, Jakob, et al. [27] Proposed a new mutation operators for genetic algorithm and used for evolving instances of the symmetric TSP. Azezan, NurArif, et al. [28] showed the initial design of the crow search algorithm for symmetric TSP. Wei, Feng-Feng, et al [29] presented a comprehensive empirical study on GAO, ACO and PSO for symmetric TSP. Divya [30] developed Ant Search method for symmetric TSP. Klug, Nikolas, et al. [31] proposed k-Repetitive-Nearest-Neighbor algorithm which is an extension of existing Nearest-Neighbor heuristics for symmetric TSP. taněk, Rostislav, et al. [32] proposed a different heuristics improvement for "the angular-metric travelling salesman problem (AngleTSP)". Ramadhan & Imran [33] proposed a two-phased meta-heuristic approach to solve traveling repairman problem (TRP) which is a variant of symmetric TSP. Kumar, Ajendra, et al. [34] proposed a Fuzzy C-Mean Genetic Algorithm (FCMGA) for symmetric TSP. Zhong, Yiwen, et al. [35] proposed a discrete PIO (DPIO) algorithm for large-scale TSP instances. Zouari, Wiem, et al. [36] proposed hybrid ant colony algorithm for Traveling Thief Problem (TTP) which is a variant of symmetric TSP. Varadarajan & Whitley [37] proposed Mixing Genetic Algorithm for symmetric TSP instances. Peake, Joshua, et al. [38] proposed "a restricted variant of the pheromone matrix with linear memory complexity (ACO)" for large-scale symmetric TSP. Luo [39] designed Hopfield network method to solve symmetric TSP. Ban [40] proposed "a two-phase meta-heuristic which combines the Insertion Heuristic (IH), Variable Neighborhood Search (VNS) and the tabu search (TS)" to solve Time Dependent Traveling Salesman Problem (TDTSP). Weise, Thomas, et al [41] proposed a new crossover operator called BBX evolutionary Algorithms (EAs) to solve symmetric TSP instances. Yang, Hongtai, et al. [42] performed experiments to find the shortest path for symmetric TSP by using genetic algorithm (GA). Faigl, Jan, et al [43] proposed two heuristic algorithms, the first one built based on a decoupled approach for symmetric TSP, and the second is the growing self-organizing array method, the combination of two algorithms used to solve multi-goal path planning which is a variant of traveling salesman problem with neighborhoods (TSPN). Herrán, Alberto, et al. [44] proposed "a parallel General Variable Neighborhood Search (GVNS) procedure" to solve Hamiltonian p-Median Problem (HpMP) which is a generalization of symmetric TSP. Caracciolo, Sergio, et al. [45] studied and reviewed Euclidean TSP, with random cities instances. Sahana [46] proposed a hybrid model consisted of genetic algorithm (GA) and heuristics like "remove-sharp" and "local-opt" with ant colony system (ACS) to solve symmetric TSP. Koczy, Laszlo T., et al [47] proposed Triple Fuzzy Time Dependent Traveling Salesman Problem approach (3FTD TSP) for Time Dependent TSP (TD TSP). Venkatesh, Pandiri, et al. [48] proposed "a multi-start iterated local search algorithm" for maximum scatter traveling salesman problem (MSTSP). Yang & Szeto [49] used a Multi-Agent System method to solve symmetric TSP. Menezes, Breno A. M., et al [50] compared and analyzed the performance of ACO

on contemporary high-performance hardware for symmetric TSP. Attarmoghaddam, Narges, et al. [51] proposed a hardware realization of the crossover method in the genetic algorithm for symmetric (TSP). Lupoai, Vlad-Ioan, et al. [52] developed a self-organizing maps evolutionary algorithms and ACS to handle the Min_Max algorithm for MOTSP instances. Imeson & Smith [53] proposed an algorithm that combined of the state-of-the-art SAT and TSP solvers to solve multi-robot motion planning problem. Hari, S. K. K., et al. [54] Discussed unmanned vehicle routes UAV as symmetric TSP. Bhavana V, et al. [55] applied Cuckoo Search Algorithm on symmetric TSP. RenuJangra and Ramesh Kait [56] proposed modified ant system (MAS) to solve symmetric TSP. Ginting, HagaiNuansa, et al. [57] Discussed Dijkstra algorithm role in solving symmetric TSP. Switrayana, I Nyoman, et al. [58] modeled a Search optimization to find shortest path with genetic algorithms for symmetric STP and MTSP. Jasim and Ali [59] proposed "Branch and Bound technique (BABT)" to solve symmetric TSP. Manopiniwes, Wapee, et al. [60] used symmetric TSP algorithm to solve ecotourism destinations in Chiang Mai, Thailand. Ghasemi-Sardabrud, Mahsa, et al. [61] presented a numerical example to solve draft limit and time windows TSP. Jaradat, Ameera, et al. [62] proposed "Firefly Algorithm (FA) and k-means clustering" to solve symmetric TSP. Al-Omeer, Maha Ata, and ZakirHussain Ahmed [63] developed a genetic algorithm (GA) with six different crossover operators to find the optimal solutions to MOTSP. Duflo, Gabriel, et al.[64] proposed a genetic algorithm called GP hyper-heuristic to solve large scales symmetric TSP. Wang, Y., et al.[65] enhanced the discrete symbiotic organism search (DSOS) and called it the excellence coefficients and self-escape strategy (ECSDSOS) for symmetric TSP. Benavent, Enrique, et al. [66] proposed two mathematical formulations and according to authors, this is the first exact approach to pickup-and-delivery TSP. Vukmirovic, Slavomir, et al.[67] showed how to solve the transport network optimization by using Exhaustive Search Algorithm and Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP). Traub & Vygen [68] showed an improved analysis of the best-of-many Christofides algorithm for s-t-path TSP. Juneja, Sahib Singh, et al. [69] used genetic algorithm (GA) capabilities to solve symmetric TSP. Yelmewad & Talawar [70] showed a GPU-based Parallel Iterative Hill Climbing (PIHC) algorithm to solve large-scale symmetric TSP. Dahan, et al.[71] modified the flying ant colony optimization (FACO) to a new algorithm called dynamic flying ant colony optimization (DFACO) to solve symmetric TSP. Akter, Shamima, et al.[72] proposed a new crossover operator for traditional genetic algorithm to solve symmetric TSP. Ayon, Safial Islam, et al.[73] modified standard spider monkey algorithm (SMO) to solve symmetric TSP. Thenepalle & Singamsetty [74] introduced a new variant of TSP called , open close multiple travelling salesmen problem with single depot (OCMTSP). Miao, Kun, et al.[75] proposed a two-stage approach based on Kernighan–Helsgaun (LKH) algorithm to solve the one-commodity traveling salesman problem with selective pickup and delivery (1-TSP-SELPD). Tawhid & Savsani [76] ,proposed discrete sine-cosine algorithm (DSCA) which is an extension of (SCA) to solve symmetric TSP. Kongzhi [77] proposed An evolutionary multi-objective optimization called non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm II (NSGAI) to solve

symmetric TSP. Paul, Victor, et al.[78] discussed new proposed strategies in genetic algorithm (GA) used to solve symmetric TSP.

Jakjoud, Abdeslam, et al. [79] proposed a new heuristic algorithm called, Spores Algorithm (SPA) to solve symmetric TSP. Madani&Ndiaye[80] used the General Algebraic Modeling System to solve a new type of vehicle routing problems(VRP) and a two types of a Discrete Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP) with a Moving Depot (TSP-MD). Mahjoub, A. Ridha, et al. [81] proposed a layered compact ILP formulation to solve Steiner Traveling Salesman Problems. Ahmed, Zied O., et al. [82] proposed the Camels Herd Algorithm (CHA) to solve symmetric TSP. Traub&Vygen [83] used 32 approach to solve s-t-path TSP. Platz [84] discussed and analyzed A multi-depot TSP using graph theory. Dong, Ruyi, et al. [85] proposed new hybrid algorithm based on wolf pack search and local search (WPS-LS) to solve symmetric TSP. Choong, Shin Siang, et al.[86] proposed a hyper-heuristic method, called Modified Choice Function (MCF)based on bee colony algorithm , to solve symmetric TSP. Karaboga&Gorkemli [87] presented new versions of artificial bee colony (ABC) to solve symmetric TSP. Taillard&Helsgaun [88] applied “Partial OPTimizationMetaheuristic under special Intensification Conditions” method called (POPMUSIC) to solve large-scale symmetric TSP. Kaabi&Harrath[89] proposed a new permutation rules for genetic algorithm(GA) to solve symmetric TSP. Ra, N.a., et al.[90] proposed an enhanced algorithm called modernised genetic (MGA-TSP) to solve Symmetric TSP. Hossam, Anass, et al. [91] proposed a meta-heuristic algorithm called Elephant Herding Optimization (EHO) to solve symmetric TSP. Jafari[92] discussed asymmetric travelling salesman problem (ATSP) as a single commodity flow problem. Cooper &Nicolescu[93] discussed (said) algorithm ,and provided a suggested algorithm to solve symmetric TSP. Muchammad&Asep [94] Applied Branch and Bound algorithm on a specific symmetric TSP case study. Wang, Xingyin, et al.[95], improved Steiner Zone Variable Neighborhood Search heuristic algorithm (SZVNS) to solve Close-Enough Traveling Salesman Problem (CETSP). Almahasneh, Ruba, et al. [96] proposed Intuitionistic Fuzzy Time Dependent Traveling Salesman Problem (IFTD TSP) to solve Time Dependent TSP ((TD TSP). X. Chen, Y. Liu, X. Li et al.[97] proposed an improved genetic algorithm to solve multi-objective traveling salesman problem (MOTSP). Li, Hang, et al. [98] proposed an enhanced version of Wolf colony search algorithm to solve symmetric tsp. Rahman&Jinwen [99] proposed a dynamical route construction algorithm to solve symmetric and a symmetric TSP. Othman, Abdoun, et al. [100] proposed a hybrid algorithm combined of ACO and GA to solve MOTSP. Bouzidi& Mohammed [101] proposed an improved Cat Swarm Optimization (CSO) to solve symmetric TSP. Wei & Liu [102] proposed an enhanced particle swarm optimization based on neighborhood searching (NPSO) to solve symmetric TSP. Shi, Jialong, et al [103] showed that methods used in multi-objective optimization can solve single-objective problems like symmetric TSP.Ismail [104] applied a heuristics algorithm called Domino Algorithm and Nearest Neighbor algorithm to solve symmetric TSP.Tinarut&Leksakul [105] solved symmetric TSP by using Self-Organizing Map

(SOM), which is Artificial Neural Networks algorithm (ANN). Soukaina et al [106] proposed mathematical heuristic formulation to solve “The Close Enough Travelling Salesman Problem with Time Window (CETSP-TW)”. Saliı [107] Revisited dynamic programming method to solve the precedence constrained traveling salesman problem (TSP-PC). Alanzi&Bennaceur [108] proposed “a general platform based on HadoopMapReduce approach for implementing parallel genetic algorithms” to solve symmetric TSP. Naser, Husain, et al [109] used a multi perfect matching and partitioning methods to solve symmetric TSP. Wang, Lijin, et al [110] proposed an enhanced List-based simulated annealing (ELBSA) algorithm for solving large-scale symmetric (TSP). Poikonen, Stefan, et al. [111] used branch and bound algorithm to solve Traveling Salesman Problem with a Drone (TSP-D). Bouziaren&Aghezzaf [112] improved the augmented varepsilon -constraint and a Branch and Cut algorithm (AUGMECON2-BC) to solve traveling salesman problem with profits (TSPP). Othman, Mohamed Rafique, et al. [113] proposed a hybrid algorithm combined of the Water Flow Algorithm (WFA) and Variable Neighbourhood Search (VNS) called WFA-VNS to solve symmetric TSP. Ha, Q.M., Deville, Y., Pham, Q.D. et al. [114] proposed a hybrid genetic search algorithm to solve traveling salesman problem with drone (TSP-D). Waissi&Kaushal [115] proposed a heuristic algorithm to solve symmetric (TSP). Schmitt, João P., et al. [116] evaluated MMAS, US local search and 3-opt local search performance in solving Asymmetric and Dynamic TSP with Moving Vehicle (ADTSPMV). Cacchiani, Valentina, et al. [117] proposed a new Mixed Integer Programming model for Traveling Salesman Problem with Time-dependent Service times (TSP-TS) and developed a multi-operator genetic algorithm and two Branch-and-Cut methods, based on the proposed model. Isoart&Régın [118] corrected the drawbacks of weighted circuit constraint (WCC) by introducing the Hamiltonian cycle constraint associated with propagators to solve symmetric TSP. Alipour&Razavi [119] developed a novel local heuristic search ,based on nearest insertion into the convex hull construction heuristic NICH-LS to solve Euclidean TSP. Chen, Zhixiang, et al. [120] proposed an exponential time approximation scheme for the symmetric (TSP) on undirected graphs. Köhne, Anna, et al. [121] discussed constant integrality ratio in the asymmetric TSP. Jedrzejowicz&Wierzbowska[122] presented a novel application of Apache Spark to solve symmetric TSP. Chlebík&Chlebíková [123] presented the weighted amplifiers and weighted low occurrence methods to solve symmetric TSP. Liu, Qingxue, et al. [124] proposed “a niching particle swarm optimization (PSO)-based Euclidean distance and hierarchical clustering (EDHC) for multimodal optimization” (EDHC-PSO) to solve symmetric TSP. Siemiński [125] discussed the usefulness of Ant Colony Communities (ACC) in solving dynamic TSP (DSTP). Zenklusen, [126] presented 1.5-approximation for the Metric Path Traveling Salesman Problem (Path TSP). Leong, KahHuo, et al [127] presented an optimization algorithm and mathematical model based on the foraging behavior of bees and decision theory to solve a railway traveling salesman problem (RTSP).Khanra, Aditi, et al. [128] proposed a hybrid algorithm combined of ACO and GA to solve discrete multi-objective TSP (MOTSP).

Literature Analysis

We reviewed 200 articles published in year 2019 (Scopus database) related to TSP; from the 200 reviewed papers we found that only 128 papers have a direct relation to TSP. The literature analysis showed the TSP variants that have been discussed in published articles in the year 2019; 34 variants were mentioned see table 1.

Table 1. TSP variants

No	TSP variant	Number of articles
1	Different Symmetric TSP (small , medium and large instances)	82
2	Multi-Objective TSP (MOTSP)	7
3	Roaming Salesman Problem (RSP)	1
4	Multi-commodity Traveling Salesman Problem with Priority Prizes (MTSPPP).	1
5	Moving Target TSP (MT-TSP).	1
6	Biased-TSP-Path	1
7	TSP with Time Windows (TSPTW)	2
8	open-loop variant TSP	1
9	the angular-metric travelling salesman problem (AngleTSP)	1
10	Traveling Thief Problem (TTP) which is a variant of symmetric TSP.	1
11	Time Dependent Traveling Salesman Problem (TDTSP)	1
12	traveling salesman problem with neighborhoods (TSPN)	1
13	Euclidean TSP	4
14	Time Dependent TSP (TD TSP)	2
15	Maximum scatter traveling salesman problem (MSTSP).	1

16	pickup-and-delivery TSP	1
17	s-t-path TSP	1
18	Open close multiple travelling salesman problem with single depot (OCMTSP).	1
19	One-commodity traveling salesman problem with selective pickup and delivery (1-TSP-SELPD).	1
20	Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP) with a Moving Depot (TSP-MD).	1
21	Steiner Traveling Salesman Problems.	1
22	s-t-path TSP	1
23	multi-depot TSP	1
24	asymmetric travelling salesman(ATSP)	2
25	Close-Enough Traveling Salesman Problems (CETSP).	1
26	precedence constrained traveling salesman problem (TSP-PC)	1
27	Traveling Salesman Problem with a Drone (TSP-D)	2
28	traveling salesman problem with profits (TSPP).	1
29	Asymmetric and Dynamic TSP with Moving Vehicle (ADTSPMV)	1
30	Traveling Salesman Problem with Time-dependent Service times (TSP-TS)	1
31	dynamic TSP (DSTP)	1
32	Metric Path Traveling Salesman Problem (Path TSP).	1
33	railway traveling salesman problem (RTSP)	1
34	half-integer TSP	1

82 articles from 128 were for symmetric TSP with ratio of 64%, and 46 articles were for other different types of TSP with ratio of 36% see figure 2.

Figure 2: ratio of symmetric TSP to other variants.

The literature analysis showed new proposed algorithms, improved existing algorithms and applying existing algorithms in to different variants. The presented algorithms were used to solve different variants of TSP. The other 72 articles were for other optimization problems and mentioned TSP.

The literature review for 128 articles showed the following proposed and improved algorithms (see table 2.)

Table 2 the proposed /improved algorithms for TSP in the year 2019

No	Algorithm name	Reference	TSP type
1	dynamic spider monkey optimization (DSMO)(new variant)	[1]	large symmetric TSP instances
2	a hybrid heuristic algorithm	[2]	a variant of symmetric TSP called , flying sidekick TSP
3	a hybrid algorithm , called (MOTSRP)	[3]	Multi-Objective Traveling Repairman Problem (MOTRP)
4	a two-phase matheuristic algorithm	[4]	Roaming Salesman Problem (RSP).
5	a heuristic algorithm, with a binomial distribution model	[5]	symmetric TSP

6	network reconstruction technique with minimal spanning tree (MST)	[6]	symmetric TSP
7	a cantor-set based (CB) method for heuristic algorithms	[7]	symmetric TSP
8	adaptive and modular genetic algorithm (AMGA)	[8]	symmetric TSP
9	a multi-objective genetic algorithm (MOGA)	[9]	symmetric TSP
10	a self-exploration strategy added to chicken swarm algorithm	[10]	symmetric TSP
11	a virtual graph(algorithm A* and graph Hamilton circuit)	[11]	symmetric TSP
12	Biased Random-Key Genetic Algorithm (BRKGA)	[12]	Medium and large Multi-commodity Traveling Salesman Problem with Priority Prizes (MTSPPP).
13	hybrid algorithm(modified particle swarm optimization (PSO) and genetic algorithm (GA)	[17]	symmetric and asymmetric TSP
14	a two new operators ("link swap and 3-permute")	[18]	open-loop variant TSP.
15	improved k-OPT heuristic algorithm	[19]	symmetric TSP
16	improved classical TSP algorithm[an iterative solution method]	[20]	symmetric TSP
17	Non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm II (NSGA-II)	[21]	multi-objective TSP (MOTSP)
18	Greedy Randomized Adaptive Search Procedure (GRASP)	[22]	symmetric TSP
19	heuristic model (frequency graph)	[23]	symmetric TSP

20	heuristic strategies(discrete optimization)	[24]	symmetric TSP
21	improved Christofides algorithm	[25]	half-integer TSP
22	new mutation operators for genetic algorithm	[27]	evolving instances of the symmetric TSP
23	Improved Ant Search method	[30]	symmetric TSP
24	k-Repetitive-Nearest-Neighbor algorithm	[31]	symmetric TSP
25	different heuristics improvement	[32]	angular-metric travelling salesman problem(AngleTSP)
26	two-phased meta-heuristic approach	[33]	symmetric TSP
27	Fuzzy C-Mean Genetic Algorithm (FCMGA)	[34]	symmetric TSP
28	discrete PIO algorithm(DPIO)	[35]	Large-scale symmetric TSP instances.
29	hybrid ant colony algorithm	[36]	Traveling Thief Problem (TTP)
30	Mixing Genetic Algorithm	[37]	symmetric TSP
31	Improved pheromone matrix with linear memory complexity (ACO)	[38]	large-scale symmetric TSP
32	Hopfield network method	[39]	symmetric TSP
33	two-phase meta-heuristic (Insertion Heuristic (IH), Variable Neighborhood Search (VNS) and the tabu search (TS))	[40]	Time Dependent Traveling Salesman Problem (TDTSP)
34	new crossover operator (BBX evolutionary Algorithms (EAs))	[41]	symmetric TSP
35	Hybrid heuristic algorithm(decoupled approach, growing self-organizing array method)	[43]	traveling salesman problem with neighborhoods (TSPN)

36	parallel General Variable Neighborhood Search (GVNS) procedure	[44]	Hamiltonian p-Median Problem (symmetric TSP)
37	hybrid model (genetic algorithm (GA) , heuristics like "remove-sharp" and" local-opt" with ant colony system (ACS))	[46]	symmetric TSP
38	Triple Fuzzy Time Dependent TSP approach (3FTD TSP)	[47]	Time Dependent TSP (TD TSP)
39	multi-start iterated local search algorithm	[48]	maximum scatter traveling salesman problem (MSTSP)
40	hardware realization of the crossover method in the genetic algorithm	[51]	symmetric TSP
41	self-organizing maps evolutionary algorithm(ACS to handle the Min_Max algorithm)	[52]	multi-objective TSP MOTSP
42	state-of-the-art SAT and TSP solvers	[53]	Symmetric TSP
43	modified ant system (MAS)	[56]	symmetric TSP
44	Branch and Bound technique (BABT)	[59]	symmetric TSP
45	Firefly Algorithm (FA) and k-means clustering	[62]	symmetric TSP
46	genetic algorithm (GA)(six different crossover operators)	[63]	multi-objective TSP MOTSP
47	GP hyper-heuristic(GA algorithm)	[64]	symmetric TSP (large-scale instances)
48	excellence coefficients and self-escape strategy (ECSDSOS)	[65]	symmetric TSP
49	A two mathematical formulations	[66]	pickup-and-delivery TSP

50	improved analysis of the best-of-many Christofides algorithm	[68]	s-t-path TSP
51	Parallel Iterative Hill Climbing (PIHC) algorithm	[70]	symmetric TSP (large-scale instances)
52	dynamic flying ant colony optimization (DFACO)	[71]	symmetric TSP
53	new crossover operator for traditional genetic algorithm	[72]	symmetric TSP
54	modified standard spider monkey algorithm (SMO)	[73]	symmetric TSP
55	two-stage approach based on Kernighan–Helsgaun (LKH) algorithm	[75]	one-commodity traveling salesman problem with selective pickup and delivery (1-TSP-SELPD).
56	discrete sine-cosine algorithm (DSCA)	[76]	Symmetric TSP
57	non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm II (NSGAI)	[77]	Symmetric TSP
58	new strategies in genetic algorithm (GA)	[78]	Symmetric TSP
59	Spores Algorithm (SPA)	[79]	Symmetric TSP
60	layered compact ILP formulation	[81]	Steiner Traveling Salesman Problems
61	Camels Herd Algorithm (CHA)	[82]	Symmetric TSP
62	new hybrid algorithm(wolf pack search and local search)(WPS-LS)	[85]	Symmetric TSP
63	Modified Choice Function (MCF)based on bee colony algorithm	[86]	Symmetric TSP
64	new versions of artificial bee colony (ABC)	[87]	Symmetric TSP

65	Partial OPTimizationMetaheuristic under special Intensification Conditions((POPMUSIC method)	[88]	symmetric TSP (large-scale instances)
66	new permutation rules for genetic algorithm(GA)	[89]	Symmetric TSP
67	modernised genetic (MGA-TSP)	[90]	Symmetric TSP
68	Elephant Herding Optimization (EHO)	[91]	Symmetric TSP
69	Steiner Zone Variable Neighborhood Search heuristic algorithm (SZVNS)	[95]	Close-Enough Traveling Salesman Problem (CETSP).
70	Intuitionistic Fuzzy Time Dependent Traveling Salesman Problem (IFTD TSP)	[96]	Time Dependent TSP ((TD TSP).
71	an improved genetic algorithm	[97]	multi-objective traveling salesman problem (MOTSP)
72	enhanced version of Wolf colony search algorithm	[98]	Symmetric TSP
73	a dynamical route construction algorithm	[99]	Symmetric and asymmetric TSP
74	hybrid algorithm (ACO and GA)	[100]	multi-objective traveling salesman problem (MOTSP)
75	an improved Cat Swarm Optimization (CSO)	[101]	Symmetric TSP
76	enhanced particle swarm optimization	[102]	Symmetric TSP
77	mathematical heuristic formulation	[106]	The Close Enough Travelling Salesman Problem with Time Window (CETSP-TW)
78	a general platform based on HadoopMapReduce approach for	[108]	Symmetric TSP

	implementing parallel genetic algorithms		
79	enhanced List-based simulated annealing (ELBSA)	[110]	symmetric TSP (large-scale instances)
80	improved augmented varepsilon - constraint and a Branch and Cut algorithm (AUGMECON2-BC)	[112]	traveling salesman problem with profits (TSPP).
81	a hybrid algorithm (WFA-VNS)	[113]	Symmetric TSP
82	hybrid genetic search algorithm	[114]	Traveling salesman problem with drone (TSP-D).
83	heuristic algorithm	[115]	Symmetric TSP
84	new Mixed Integer Programming (multi-operator genetic algorithm and two Branch-and-Cut methods)	[117]	Traveling Salesman Problem with Time-dependent Service times (TSP-TS)
85	a novel local heuristic search(NICH-LS)	[119]	Euclidean TSP
86	an exponential time approximation scheme	[120]	Symmetric TSP
87	novel application of Apache Spark	[122]	Symmetric TSP
88	a niching particle swarm optimization (PSO) (EDHC-PSO)	[124]	Symmetric TSP
89	hybrid algorithm(ACO and GA)	[128]	discrete multi-objective TSP (MOTSP)

From 128 related papers, we found that 89 articles were for new proposed and improved algorithms that used to solve different variants of TSP; 58 from 89 articles were for symmetric TSP see figure 3.

Figure 3: ratio for proposed algorithms for symmetric TSP.

Symmetric TSP got 65.1% ratio from the new proposed and improved algorithms; the other TSP variants got 34.9%. Table 2 also showed that 25 articles proposed genetic (GA) based algorithms with ratio of 28%, proposed Heuristic algorithms in general without determining exact name mentioned in 16 articles, ant colony optimization mentioned in 8 articles, and the rest of articles were for many different types of proposed algorithms. The rest of related Articles (39 article) discussed and compared existing algorithms to find their performance in finding optimal solutions for different TSP see table 3 for more explanations.

Table 3: References discussed TSP in the year 2109

No	Reference no	Objective	Results	TSP variants
1	[13]	Compared GA , ACO and simulated annealing optimization	genetic algorithm performance was better	Moving Target TSP (MT-TSP).
2	[14]	discussed path version of the TSP	Proved that the Biased-TSP-Path is approximable within a constant factor	Biased-TSP-Path
3	[15]	discussed TSP with Time Windows by applying QUBO formulation	actual execution of small scale TSPTW instances on the D-Wave platform	small scale TSPTW instances
4	[16]	Discussed variance estimates for TSP Cn	“proved that if the cities are well-connected in a	Euclidean TSP

			certain sense, then TSP C_n appropriately centered and scaled converges to zero in probability”	
5	[26]	Discussed Exponential Time Hypothesis in Hamiltonian cycle	improve the 32 best-known bounds for general graphs	symmetric TSP
6	[28]	Discussed initial design of the crow search algorithm	results show the significant and feasible solution	symmetric TSP
7	[29]	a comprehensive empirical study on GAO, ACO and PSO	some guidance for designing efficient evolutionary algorithms to solve TSP	symmetric TSP
8	[42]	experiments to find the shortest path for symmetric TSP	constructed models can be used to estimate the travel time variance and reliability	symmetric TSP
9	[45]	reviewed Euclidean TSP	optimal cost is a self-averaging quantity	Euclidean TSP
10	[49]	used a Multi-Agent System	TSP solver used is based on genetic algorithm	symmetric TSP
11	[50]	compared and analyzed the performance of ACO on contemporary high-performance hardware	there is no overall best parallelization strategy	symmetric TSP
12	[54]	Discussed unmanned vehicle routs UAV as symmetric TSP	the average computation time required to solve the problem	UAV as a Symmetric TSP

13	[55]	applied Cuckoo Search Algorithm	“A thorough analysis has been performed to assess the efficacy of this optimization”	symmetric TSP
14	[57]	Discussed Dijkstra algorithm	Dijkstra algorithm must be modified using Dijkstra's priority clustering	symmetric TSP
15	[58]	modeled a Search optimization	find the shortest path with genetic algorithms	symmetric STP , MTSP
16	[60]	used symmetric TSP algorithm to solve ecotourism destinations in Chiang Mai, Thailand	Benefits of TSP technique to the tourism context	symmetric TSP
17	[61]	presented a numerical example	obtained the best possible route	draft limit and time windows TSP
18	[67]	solve the transport network optimization using TSP and Exhaustive Search Algorithm	identify multiple optimal solutions	symmetric TSP
19	[69]	used genetic algorithm (GA)	Obtain convergence of genetic algorithm	symmetric TSP
20	[74]	Presented a new variant of TSP and find optimal route	computational experiments have been carried out on some benchmark	open close multiple travelling salesman problem with single depot (OCMTSP)
21	[80]	used the General Algebraic Modeling System	a new class of vehicle routing problems	(TSP) with a Moving Depot (TSP-MD).
22	[83]	used 3/2 approach	compute a spanning tree (V, S)	s-t-path TSP
23	[84]	discussed and analyzed A multi-	TS games is analyzed by	A multi-depot TSP

		depot TSP using graph theory	characterizing graphs and digraphs	
24	[92]	Discussed asymmetric travelling salesman problem (ATSP) as a single commodity flow problem.	solving certain real world instances by standard integer programming methods	Asymmetric TSP
25	[93]	discussed (said) algorithm	provides an example application of TSP algorithm	symmetric TSP
26	[94]	Applied Branch and Bound algorithm	small error level with a long calculations	symmetric TSP
27	[103]	showed methods used in multi-objective optimization	solve single-objective problems	symmetric TSP
28	[104]	applied Domino Algorithm and Nearest Neighbor algorithm	finding the optimal results by which the application will be moreover quite simple and easy	symmetric TSP
29	[105]	solve symmetric TSP by using Self-Organizing Map (SOM),	Improve the processing time	symmetric TSP
30	[107]	Discussed dynamic programming method	prove the validity of DP optimality for TSP-PC	Precedence constrained traveling salesman problem (TSP-PC).
31	[109]	used a multi perfect matching and partitioning methods	Get optimum or near-optimum solutions in polynomial execution time	symmetric TSP
32	[111]	used branch and bound algorithm	provide additional variants of heuristic approach	Traveling Salesman Problem with a Drone (TSP-D).
33	[116]	EvaluateMMAS, US local search and 3-opt	MMAS-US is the best algorithm while	Asymmetric and Dynamic TSP with

		local search performance	for ADTSPMV the MMAS-3opt is the most suitable	Moving Vehicle (ADTSPMV).
34	[118]	corrected the drawbacks of weighted circuit constraint (WCC) by introducing the Hamiltonian cycle constraint	a strong reduction of the computation time	symmetric TSP
35	[121]	discussed constant integrality ratio	ATSP node-weighted instances and unweighted digraph instances are almost equivalent	Asymmetric TSP
36	[123]	Discussed the weighted amplifiers and weighted low occurrence methods	show that already slight improvement of known expander values modestly improve the current best approximation hardness value for TSP	symmetric TSP
37	[125]	discussed the usefulness of Ant Colony Communities (ACC)	Showed that the routes are far shorter than in the case of original colonies	Dynamic TSP (DSTP).
38	[126]	Showed 1.5-approximation for the Metric Path Traveling Salesman	progress on the approximability of Path TSP will also lead to an improvement for TSP.	Path Traveling Salesman Problem (Path TSP).
39	[127]	presented an optimization algorithm and mathematical model based on the foraging behavior of bees and decision theory	proved the reliability and capability of the route planning and optimization solutions for RSs	railway traveling salesman problem (RTSP)

Table 3 show that 21 articles from 39 discussed symmetric TSP, where 18 articles discussed other different variants of TSP.

Conclusion

In this research 200 articles were reviewed from Scopus data base, only 128 were having a direct relation to TSP, the other 72 articles were for another optimization problems and mentioned word (TSP). The reviewed literature mentioned 34 different variants of TSP. Symmetric TSP got the highest ratio (64%) from the related (128) reviewed articles. The literature showed that 89 articles proposed or improved new algorithms, Symmetric TSP got 65.1% ratio from the new proposed and improved algorithms, 34.9% for the other TSP variants. The literature also showed that genetic based proposed algorithms got 28% from the reviewed articles. Many exiting heuristic algorithms were improved and enhanced to solve different types of TSP. Finally we conclude that most of published articles were for symmetric TSP and also the proposed and enhanced were algorithms for symmetric TSP. We hope that this research considered as a road map for more research in this field in the future

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